

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PREPARING SPECIALISTS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES ON THE BASIS OF A DUAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. *Outstanding achievements in science and technology serve to radically improve the quality of life of people, while creating other conditions for social, economic, cultural, material and technical and vital activity, realizing their personal needs and interests. Mobile communications, personal computers, personal equipment and all kinds of service equipment, modern information and communication technologies are based on the scientific and technological progress of mankind, which is spoken of today in terms of technical changes.*

Keywords: *dual education, professional education, professional activity, professional development, mobile communication.*

In our country, systematic reforms are being implemented on the formation of educational content, integration of science and production on the basis of a dual system. In the strategy of Action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is important to develop mechanisms for assessing the quality of education, increase the availability and efficiency of educational services, and to ensure the implementation of such priorities as “establishing a wide range of training and teaching the necessary specialties”, it is necessary to study a holistic and systematic integrative knowledge, formation of professional skills and from this point of view, the state of preparation of professional education specialists and production personnel for professional activities, research their professional competence in areas of specialization and areas of production, develop innovative methods of pedagogical diagnosis and introduce them into practice.

When developing the theoretical framework for the construction of a dual system of preparing future professional education specialists for professional activities in higher educational institutions, we came from the point of view of its suitability for the following:

- social production needs of educational goals;
- organizational approach to the foundations of socio-philosophical, scientific basics of educational activities;
- the didactic foundations of the methodological feature of engineering and pedagogical professional education.

Clarification of the basic, conceptually significant ideas that meet these requirements was carried out on the basis of principles of “internal”, phenomenological and methodological, as well as social pedagogical nature, which have a decisive influence on the development of professional education as a special integrative sphere of professional education.

There are many points of view regarding the most likely or optimal structural structure of the system of Continuing Professional Education. In this, many variants of territorial and sectoral systems have appeared, the variety of which can be divided into three types:

- organizational and functional structural structure of continuous professional education;
- systematic continuous professional content;
- self-developing system. In this regard, any structure of dual education as a theoretical basis for preparing professional education specialists for professional activities on the basis of a dual system on our part is considered incomplete if it is not comparable to the traditional system of education.

If dual education is a new paradigm according to most experts, what are the reasons of its difference from the previous one, in what aspects and dimensions does it move from one to the next; whether dual education is simply a violation of the traditional educational system or a dialectical denial of it and is finally checked for the most serious and truthful examination in time?

In our view, dual education in reality consists of a new content-essence paradigm of educational development, representing a break from the old educational paradigm, which is usually called traditional, in a sufficiently radical (sharp) way. In other words, the concept of education, its purpose, essence, tasks, principles and organizational structure are revised. Table 1 provides a comparative description of the validity and development of the principles of educational development in the traditional and continuous paradigm. In particular, it is argued that the dual system of education dialectically negates the discrete system of education that had previously occurred conventionally.

In contrast to the traditional method of education, which is limited by the limits of material production, on the contrary, the new method determines the pace of development, provides the quality of education in close connection with practical activities to certain types of activities.

The traditional system of education deepens and defines social disparity between people. It is evaluated as a means of obtaining certain social benefits. Therefore, only a small number of people reach the upper echelons of education. The dual education system makes it possible to overcome social differences developing the abilities of each person.

The existing educational system is focused on the performance of certain tasks that are clearly present in the production and social conditions, and the professional competence of future teachers is served by the formation of the system. All the distinguished levels of dual system representation have different natures, representing different manifestations, properties, aspects of education in terms of zero quality.

These are: valuable-purposeful, systematic procedural, subjectively consequential. At this time, each of them can be considered as a separate system. From the point of view of our research, the systematic aspect of engineering and pedagogical professional education requires, first of all, its consideration as a professional-oriented system of Professional Education, which, in turn, is considered one of the educational systems of the country.

The concept of an educational system includes the internal structure of education, its construction, nature, as well as interaction, which allows to transform objects of a large number of different natures into a single holistic whole – system. As a result of the analysis of the presented descriptions, it is possible to determine the conditions for the emergence of a competency-based approach to education specific to the dual educational system:

- knowledge is given in various forms as a product of research and thinking, activities to be able to perform, the process of creation, systematically, cooperatively, generalizing practice with theory;

- the educator manifests as a "manager", "partner", that is, takes the position of cooperating, democratically influencing, helping, encouraging, being attentive to the student's personal initiatives, striving to develop his personality;

- focused on active cooperation with professors and students, creating an environment of mutual support and mutual responsibility;

-through group forms of organization of education and upbringing, conditions are created for those who receive education so that they can practically master various forms of interpersonal relations and communication, feel the joy of working in cooperation and creation;

-refusal to assess the suitability of actions and behavior for a predetermined pattern.

The new system of education uses the problematic method of communication as the main method of education. It is creative in nature, making its goal not only to give knowledge, but also to teach them to use it. It is for this reason that practical work serves as an important gift for learning. The dual system of engineering and pedagogical professional education, built on the basis of the interconnection of two independent spheres, such as production and the educational sphere, provides optimal conditions for the mutual transformation of engineering and pedagogical activities. In fact, the third idea of conceptual significance, which ensures the feasibility of building a dual system of professional education, based on the methodological nature of higher education, can be explained as follows: the dual restructuring of the educational system in the process of professional training of engineering and pedagogical personnel ensures the integrability of Professional Education, expressing its systemic integrity.

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